

DYNAMICS OF THE GEOMAGNETIC FIELD ON THE TERRITORY OF UKRAINE AND IN THE AREA OF AKADEMIK VERNADSKY STATION ACCORDING TO THE RESULTS OF CALCULATIONS AND EXPERIMENTAL DATA

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The Earth's magnetic field is one of the main information factors in the study of its internal (core, mantle, lithosphere) and external (atmosphere, ionosphere, magnetosphere) spheres. The Earth's internal magnetic field is the vector sum of the main magnetic field B_{IGRF} (field of the Earth's core) and the anomalous magnetic field ΔB (field of the Earth's lithosphere). The most general characteristic of the internal geomagnetic field is the modulus of the induction vector B . A technology was proposed for constructing maps of the induction modulus of the geomagnetic field for an arbitrary epoch, taking into account the exact initial data of the modulus B , the change in the B_{IGRF} field, and the calculation of the magnitude of the biasing effect due to age variation. The development of such maps for different epochs allows us to assess changes in the geomagnetic field, which are caused by geodynamic and fluid processes in the Earth's lithosphere. Using this technique, a map of the module and its anomalies for Ukrainian territory was created for the epoch 2024.5.

For the territory in the area of the Ukrainian Antarctic station "Akademik Vernadsky" (UAS AV), a digital map of the module and anomalies of the geomagnetic field induction module for the epoch 2008 was developed. In 2023–2024, experimental measurements of the magnetic field induction module B were performed at more than 25 points in the area of the station AV. Based on the results of these works, the module and anomalies of the geomagnetic field induction module for the epoch 2023,5 were calculated. The obtained module and anomalies of the geomagnetic field induction module were compared with their calculated values using the above technology.

According to the results of the study for the time interval 1958,5–2023,5. A fundamentally different nature of geomagnetic field changes was revealed for the territory of Ukraine and in the area of the UAS AV station: according to the “Kyiv” geomagnetic observatory, the geomagnetic field induction modulus B increased by 2000 nT (49060÷51060), and according to the “Argentine Islands” observatory, it decreased by more than 6180 nT (42140÷35960).

Over the past 15 years (2008.5÷2023.5), the trend of magnetic field changes in Ukraine and in the area of UAC AV has persisted, but the increase in the field in Ukraine has accelerated somewhat (to ~60 nT/Year compared to ~30 nT/Year in 1958.5), and in the area of UAS AV it has slowed down slightly (to ~82 nT/Year compared to ~120 nT/Year in 1958.5).

The detected changes in the anomalous magnetic field in the area of the UAS AV station vary within insignificant limits and may be due to geodynamic and fluid lithospheric processes, including “feedbacks” to changes in tectonic stress, seismic events, and glacier movement.